

12+

Interactive Sessions

5+

Keynote Lectures

50+

Plenary Lectures

5+

Workshops

20+

Exhibitors

B2B Meetings

conferenceseries.com

4th International Conference on

Advances in Biotechnology and Bioscience

November 15-17, 2018 Berlin, Germany

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Invitation

Dear Attendees,

We are glad to announce the 4th International Conference on Advances in Biotechnology and Bioscience to be held in November 15-17, 2018 Berlin, Germany organized by Conference Series llc LTD, UK in collaboration with generous support and cooperation from enthusiastic academicians and editorial Board Members.

Adv.Biotech 2018 offers a premier forum to inspire collaboration among biologists and to share trans-disciplinary Biological thinking to unravel the underlying cellular and molecular mechanisms in health, disease and medicine.

The theme of the conference is "Integrating new advancements in the field of Biotechnology and Biosciences" and topics for discussion are Bioscience, Agriculture Bioscience, Biochemical Engineering, Biotechnology and Biomaterials science, Biomedical Science, Biopharmaceutics and Biochemistry, Bioprocess and Biological Engineering, Cell Biology, Computational Biology & Systems Biology, Drug Discovery and Delivery, Food Science, Genetics, Genomics and Proteomics, Immunology and Inflammation, Microbiology, Molecular Biology, Molecular Biotechnology, Molecular Plant Sciences and Ecology, Tissue Engineering & Stem cell research, Nano-Biotechnology, BioScience Market.

As the premier event, we have developed a program with your interests in mind. We have not only increased the number of opportunities for you to network with colleagues from across the world but also introduced more focused sessions that will feature cutting edge presentations, special panel discussions, and livelier interaction with industry leaders and experts. Life is full of give and take. Make it count in your professional life. Attend the Bioscience to network with your peers, exchange expertise and experiences, and arm yourself with the latest information to take your department to the next level.

We look forward to personally welcoming you to Berlin in November 2018.

Sincerely,
Adv.Biotech 2018
Organizing Committee

<http://advanced-biotechnology.biotechnologycongress.com/>

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Our International Open Access Journals

- 700+ Leading-edge Peer Reviewed Open Access Journals
- 21 Day Rapid Review Process
- 50000+ Editorial Board Team, 35000+ Reviewers team
- 30 Million Readers and High Visibility
- 1000+ Scientific Associations Collaborations
- 100000+ Likes
- Publication immediately after acceptance
- Quality and Quick editorial, review processing

Salient Features

- Easy to Submit and Review Systems
- High Quality and Fast Publishing Guaranteed
- Unbiased, quality-oriented, and transparent reviews
- Truly impartial recognition of the best papers
- Feedback on the impact of every article
- Enhanced feature: Audio version of published paper
- Digital articles to share and explore
- Sharing option: Social networking enabled
- Authors, reviewers and editors are provided with scientific credits
- User friendly/feasible website articles translations across more than 50 world languages

Our International Scientific Conferences

- More than 3000 Conferences happening across the globe
- Conferences organized in Medical, Pharma, Engineering, Science, Technology and Business.
- CME/CPD Accredited Conferences fostering professional and Personal development
- Continuum of education through organized scientific program
- Renowned speakers and scientists representing from 40 countries
- Highly Interactive sessions and Panel Discussions
- B2B Meetings offers perfect platform for Global Networking

Salient Features

- Robust on-line publicity for all the speakers and organizing committee members
- Career Guidance Workshops for students and early career researchers
- Accepted Abstracts will be published in various indexed journals
- Accepted abstracts will be labeled with a Digital Object Identification Number (DOI) provided by CrossRef
- Creation of speakers and abstracts pages in Google
- Opportunity to publish full Manuscripts in our Open Access Journals

Special Issues : All accepted abstracts will be published irrespective Conference Series Ilc LTD Journals

Each abstract will be provided with digital Object Identifier by

About Us

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About Conference

Adv.Biotech2018Conferencewebsiteisattracting25000+Genetics,GenomicsandMolecularBiology online visitors ranging from Researchers, Academicians and Business professionals, who are working in this field. This unique opportunity that we extend to our speakers and attendees is not being offered by any other conference organizers. Through this the abstracts and research profiles of our speakers and organizing committee members getting global visibility which is an additional feature that you would be receiving in addition to networking opportunities before, during and after the conference.

Adv.Biotech 2018 salient features

- Meet Academia and Industry visionaries to get inspired
- Expand your knowledge and find solutions to problems
- Knowledge, Benchmarking and Networking offered at one place
- Forge connections and for global networking
- Highly Organized and Structured Scientific programs
- Poster presentations and world class exhibitions
- Meet with new vendors and suppliers

How Conference Series Conferences differs from others?

- 3000+ Conferences across the globe in 30+ countries all through the year
- Over 25 Million+ Visitors and 20000+ Unique Visitors per conference
- Participation by stalwarts from various international societies
- Internationally renowned speakers and scientists representation
- Career guidance for early career researchers and students
- Interesting scientific deliberations and discussions
- Perfect platform for Global Networking

Goals

- The conference program emphasizes evidence-based practice, educational innovation, practical application, and peer to peer networking and collaboration. The goals of the conference is to provide a transformative professional development experience through
- Bringing together the world's scientific experts to catalyze and advance scientific knowledge about Genomics and Molecular Biology present the most recent research findings, and promote and enhance scientific collaborations around the world.
- Bringing together community leaders, scientists, and policy leaders to promote and enhance programmatic collaborations to more effectively address regional, national and local responses to Elderly Population around the world and overcome barriers that limit access to care and services.

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About Conference

Objectives

After participating in this meeting, attendees should be able to

- Discuss emerging issues in Genomics and Molecular Biology
- Discuss and apply recent research findings related to Genomics and Molecular Biology
- Reflect on the place of critical distance in Genomics and Molecular Biology

Who should attend

Biotechnology Researchers, New Bioscience Technologies Developers, Experts in Biology, Biotechnologists, Pharmaceutical Experts, Experts in Medication Discovery and development, Biotechnology and Industry Professionals, Experts in Organic and Inorganic Chemistry, Medical Biochemistry Experts, life sciences Industry Professionals and Scholars in Biotechnology and related areas and others engaged in endeavors related to Bioscience research and business.

About hosting organization

Conference Series is the world's leading specialist in organizing Academic, Scientific and Business conferences, meetings, symposiums and exhibitions in different verticals and horizontal like Medical, Pharma, Engineering, Science, Technology and Business to promote scientific research. Every year we host more than 3000+ global events inclusive of 1000+ Conferences 1000+ Symposiums 1000+ Workshops in USA, Europe, Middle East and Asia with the generous support and cooperation from our 30000+ Editorial Board Members, 1000+ Scientific Societies. All the conference proceedings are published in the special issues of our 700+ Open Access International Journals with the DOI provided by Crossref

Major Sessions

- Biotechnology
- Plant & Agricultural Biotechnology
- Food & Nutritional Biotechnology
- Aqua Culture & Marine Biotechnology
- Bioscience
- Biomedical Science
- Cell Biology & Immunology
- Genetics
- Tissue Engineering & Stem cell Research
- Biopharmaceutics & Biochemistry
- Food Science
- Industrial Biotechnology
- Health & Pharmaceutical Biotechnology
- Medicinal Biotechnology & Biomedical Engineering
- Environmental Biotechnology
- Nano Biotechnology
- Biosafety & Bioethics
- Biomass & Bioenergy
- Biotechnology & Biomaterial Science
- Biotechnology & Molecular Biology
- Biotechnology Market

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Supporting Journals

- Journal of Biotechnology & Biomaterials
- Journal of Biology and Medicine
- Journal of Bioremediation & Biodegradation

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About Berlin

Berlin is the capital and the largest city of Germany, as well as one of its 16 constituent states. With a steadily growing population of approximately 3.7 million. Berlin is the second most populous city proper in the European Union behind London and the seventh most populous urban area in the European Union. Berlin is a world city of culture, politics, media and science. Its economy is based on high-tech firms and the service sector, encompassing a diverse range of creative industries, research facilities, media corporations and convention venues. Berlin is home to world-renowned universities, orchestras, museums, and entertainment venues, and is host to many sporting events. Berlin is known for its numerous cultural institutions, many of which enjoy international reputation. Young people, international artists and entrepreneurs continued to settle in the city and made Berlin a popular entertainment centre in the world. Berlin has a long history of discoveries in medicine and innovations in medical technology. The modern history of medicine has been significantly influenced by scientists from Berlin.

Berlin likewise has a casual vibe and bunches of open spaces for a much needed refresher. No city in Germany is greener than Berlin with its woodlands, lakes and sprawling parks.

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Venue & Accommodation

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Best Western Premier

Airporthotel Fontane Berlin

Jonas-Lie-Straße 5-11

15831 Berlin (Mahlow)

Contact Us

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Registrations

Academic

Only Registration: USD 599

Package A (Registration + 2 nights' Accommodation): USD 1099

Package B (Registration + 3 nights' Accommodation): USD 1299

Business

Only Registration: USD 699

Package A (Registration + 2 nights' Accommodation): USD 1199

Package B (Registration + 3 nights' Accommodation): USD 1399

Student

Student Oral: USD 499

Student Poster: USD 349

Student Delegate: USD 399

E-poster: USD 99

Important Dates

Abstract submission opens: May 08, 2018

Registration opens: May 08, 2018

Early bird registration: September 26 2018

On spot registration: November 15, 2018

To register online, please visit:

<http://advanced-biotechnology.biotechnologycongress.com/registration.php>

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